

Use of Digital Tools for ESL Undergraduate Learners: A Study

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Abstract:

In the twenty-first century, the teaching and study of English has benefited greatly from the use of modern technology. Currently, most English language teachers actively employ a range of technological devices intended to improve lesson delivery. In terms of language education, digital media have become pervasive in the classroom. It appears that today's teaching and learning were more interesting because of technological advancements. The term "e-Learning" (also known as "Technology in Education") has grown increasingly important in today's classrooms. Students in the 21st century receive a curriculum that prepares them to effectively use modern technologies. Modern learning techniques are interactive, while traditional approaches rely mostly on lectures. Blogs, the Internet, Interactive Boards, mobile phones, Skype, Twitter, and YouTube, among other recent applications of digital technologies. These have not only boosted classroom stimulation, but also the involvement and actual interactivity of the learners. The goal of this study is to catalogue the cutting-edge tools for improving English education that have been developed in recent years.

Keywords: Digital tools, English language learning, modern language teaching techniques, e-learning methods, etc.,

In the conventional classroom, where English as a foreign language is taught in India, teachers are the only ones who may impart knowledge to their students. The educators took front stage, while the students played the role of silent bystanders. This idea has progressed in modern times. The emphasis of class time has shifted to the students. Teachers assist learning in the classroom and possibly beyond formal learning environments by their efforts and key tasks as the classroom manager, counsellor, and a model in the use of the language they teach.

The innovative use of techniques, apparatus, resources, systems, and tactics that are directly related to the teaching of the English language and help students achieve their goals is one way to broadly define the use of modern technology in teaching English. Because of the numerous opportunities it provides to enhance the content and delivery of the pedagogies typically used in conventional ESL classrooms, technology is now widely acknowledged as an essential educational and supplementary tool in a wide range of teaching and learning contexts. This is particularly true of English language instruction. This is achieved mostly through

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providing ample opportunities for both the student and the instructor to review content multiple times, as needed until all questions and concerns are resolved.

Technology fluency includes the ability to operate today's most popular home products and the know-how to practise cutting-edge educational systems and teaching techniques that hasten and broaden one's education.

Current educational ideas suggest that students will have more success in their language studies if they make use of the technological tools at their disposal. Incorporating technology into English lessons helps students develop a holistic understanding of the ways in which modern systems function and the relationships between their various parts. As a result, given the exceptional progress in many disciplines, it is imperative that English language training make advantage of modern technologies. Computerization, multi-media devices, mobile phones, audio/visual effects applications, and social media are just a few examples of how the education sector can keep up with the worldwide technological revolution and better support English language instruction and teacher-student connections in the classroom. The Internet makes available a vast array of useful tools, resources, and apps that can improve the quality of English instruction and learning. While it is true that many students have access to these resources, it is also important to recognise the crucial role that instructors play in implementing the numerous instructional strategies at their disposal. In addition, many of these courses aim to improve students' understanding of the English language and their command of the language as a whole.

E-Learning was initially proposed by Jay Cross in 1999. Internet-based training, web-based training, online learning, network learning, and distance learning are all terms that have developed as a result of technical progress and advancement (Yoon 2012). Doris Holzberger et al. (2013) state, digital learning is the provision of learning contents and teaching methods over the Internet in the form of digital forms of media (such as texts or images) with the intention of enhancing teaching effectiveness or promoting individual knowledge and abilities.

The limitations of time, place, and schedule were transcended and learner-centered, customised instruction was achieved through the use of computers and network technology media in learning circumstances including synchronous and asynchronous network learning. (Kaklamanou et al., 2012). Digital learning is used in many fields currently because of the rapid

pace at which information and new ideas can be shared. There are various explanations, each based on a unique vantage point. The most widely accepted definition is the one put forth by the American Society for Training and Education. E-learning is defined as "the use of electronic resources for instructional purposes. Digital media includes the World Wide Web, company networks, computers, satellite transmission, audio and video tapes, interactive television, and compact discs" (Kaila 2012).

Learning through computer and network, online instruction, and synchronous group work are all a part of this implementation. According to Anttila et al. (2012), "digital learning" refers to the use of any electronic device to acquire digital course materials for use with either wired or wireless networks, whether online or offline. (Hockly, 2012). As a result, the existing body of literature demonstrates that scholars from different countries have different opinions on online education. Digital education can be broken down into four distinct subfields by studying the findings of various academics. (Keane, 2012).

The importance of students being able to glean information from digital course materials is emphasised. By "digital teaching material content," we mean things like digitised texts and data sets. The use of digital tools including computers, laptops, tablets, and smartphones for educational purposes is highlighted. It stresses that a learner's educational activity could be sent via the Internet (or other networks) or beamed through satellite. Independent study is based on the idea that students can use digital resources to learn anything, anywhere, whenever they want to. It places a premium on, and requires students to engage in, independent study before engaging in any formal instruction.

The omnipresent nature of technology in the 21st century means that people are faced with novel opportunities and challenges. Today's schools must foster "learning to learn," or the acquisition of the knowledge and skills that make possible lifelong learning, rather than simply serving as conduits for the transmission of a predetermined set of information from teacher to student over a predetermined period of time. Therefore, it is incumbent upon educators to adjust to contemporary needs.

The time has come to empower the populace with English language skills, and this may be done with the help of the correct mix of traditional classroom instruction and online resources (modern technologies). Traditional modes of instruction have been challenged by the

introduction of e-learning tools into classrooms. E-learning, or electronic learning, refers to a wide range of technical resources that can be used by creative and skilled educators to enhance traditional classroom settings. These are employed to enliven, motivate, stimulate, and impart deeper significance to the educational experience for the students. The widespread adoption of digital tools for teaching English as a second language has led many to believe that this convergence has the potential to revolutionise education.

DIGITALIZED METHODS IN ENGLISH CLASSES

Digitalized teaching is a method of education based on traditional classroom instruction but delivered entirely online. Although traditional classroom instruction is an option, digital learning is mostly centred on the utilisation of computers and the Internet. This can also be categorized under E-learning method and can be defined as the simultaneous or asynchronous transmission of skills and knowledge to a large number of receivers over a network. It was once thought that this approach lacked the human factor essential for learning, but this was before it gained general popularity.

However, widespread acceptance has resulted from the rapid advancement of technology and the enhancement of learning methods. The advent of personal computers sparked this change, and as time has gone on, our growing reliance on mobile devices like smartphones, tablets, etc. has made them indispensable in the classroom. Electronic learning resources, such as optical discs and flash drives, are gradually replacing books. The Internet also facilitates the exchange of information around the clock, seven days a week, from any location, at any time.

INTERNET

The Internet is the most useful invention of the information age, improving our quality of life in many ways. Used extensively in the academic world for the objectives of gathering data, conducting studies, and expanding students' understanding of a wide range of topics. The Internet is become a major repository of knowledge and information.

Teachers can utilise the school's website or forum as a teaching resource if they upload their lesson plans (notes and videos) there. Tutorial videos and written notes make studying more interesting and varied. With the help of animation, PowerPoint slides, and graphics,

educators may capture the interest of their students. Many parts of English can be taught through YouTube videos, including vocabulary, accents, pronunciations, and vocal modulation. The most significant advantage of using YouTube as a teaching tool for English is the availability of real-life examples of the language in use. In the classroom, it can be used to help students develop their LSRW skills.

SKYPE

Skype has opened up a world of possibilities for teachers and students to work together, no matter where they may be physically located. It provides several opportunities for students to interact with other courses in other countries to improve their language skills. Skype allows educators to remotely guide students and help them with their work. Students can share their work with their peers by reading aloud, giving presentations, or putting on performances, and by working together on writing and research projects. In addition, they are free to pursue opportunities for personal and professional growth both inside and beyond the company.

TWITTER

Technology's gift of Twitter, a social networking tool, may be used to help students better their command of the English language. Twitter's potential as a tool for online education technology is boundless in terms of its ability to enthrall students with academic topics. Using an online education technology tool, a teacher can select from a menu of a dozen different ways to get students involved in classroom activities and boost their conceptual comprehension.

SMART-BOARDS

Teachers may project anything viewable on a computer's screen onto an interactive whiteboard, making it an ideal substitute for both traditional whiteboards and flipcharts. (such as educational software and websites). Using SMART boards, teachers may focus on the needs of individual students while teaching language arts. Reading and comprehension in language arts classes can be improved, and teachers of grammar and composition can learn new techniques, with the help of SMART Boards. By fusing video, audio, Web browsing, and word processing, a SMART Board allows teachers to engage students in collaborative learning.

MULTIPLE APPLICATIONS FOR MOBILE PHONES

Mobile phones can be used as a learning tool. Because of this, online courses can be taken at any time and from any location. It may be taken anywhere and is easy to operate.

PODCASTING

A podcast is a series of digital media files that are syndicated online and made available for listening on mobile devices and personal computers. It is easy to implement audio recordings into the teaching setting. Students in the modern era frequently utilise the Internet to watch short films, videos, and listen to music. The use of podcasts allows the educator to connect with these students in a fresh way. Furthermore, teachers can have their students watch news stations as a way to practise intonation and stress.

BLOG

Blogging's rising popularity can largely be attributed to its effectiveness as a tool for disseminating knowledge and stimulating discourse in the classroom. Many teachers now favour these innovative approaches to teaching students how to use social media in place of textbooks and traditional ways. Developing a blog for a class need not be challenging. A free blogging service like BlogSpot, WordPress, or Tumblr can serve as the blog's web server all of which are gradually increasing in their usage in India since 2019.

Since blogs may now also display graphics and some people even use them to post music and video, the instructor should encourage students to visit the blog on a regular basis. Quickly responding to student posts with a quick comment linked to the subject and inquiries about what the student has written might serve as writing prompts. Blog posts can count towards your final mark, thus participation might be mandatory. Instead of turning in written assignments to the teacher, students should be encouraged to post them on a blog.

ADVANTAGES OF USING DIGITAL-BASED LEARNING MATERIALS

The following are some of the benefits of using media in the classroom, as outlined by Kemp and Dayton (1985):

1. The standardisation of the format of instructional resources can be made possible through digital tools. Educators' understanding of a topic may differ. Since the number of possible interpretations is decreased by the use of media, messages can be transmitted consistently.

2. More interesting and fun to use while studying takes place through digital learning. Media facilitates the communication of auditory and visual information in a way that allows for the description of previously abstract and insufficient principles, concepts, processes, and procedures.
3. Educating in a setting with more interaction is possible through digital teaching. Media can be used to facilitate two-way communication between teachers and students if it is carefully selected and well-prepared. Teachers could be tempted to deliver monologues to classes without any form of media.
4. A lot of time is spent by teachers expounding upon the course materials. When used properly, media can be a time-saver. So, they can spend more time on activities and a variety of learning assignments.
5. An enhanced the level of student understanding takes place when teaching through digital tools. The usage of media not only speeds up the learning process, but also helps students retain or grasp the content better. Media allow students to learn at their own pace, in their own time, and in a variety of settings, even when teachers are unavailable.
6. Students' preferences for and enthusiasm for newly learned information, abilities, and curiosity can be bolstered by the usage of media that piques their interest.
7. Instructors can instead focus on facilitating learning rather than lecturing. They can save time by verbally explaining things instead. This means they can spend more time mentoring and guiding students.

There is a growing intertwining between the digital sphere and the classroom. Educators need to adapt to the changing knowledge landscape by taking approaches that are win-win as technology expands the possibilities for education. More and more aspects of our lives, both private and professional, depend on the availability of digital resources. Education and knowledge may now reach more kids than ever before, and students can acquire the mentality and skills they'll need to succeed in the here and now and in the future through digital learning.

Google Classroom is a free web service that aims to help schools reduce their reliance on paper by facilitating the creation, distribution, and grading of assignments. Google Classroom simplifies and expedites the educational process by facilitating file sharing between teachers and students. In this forum, students can ask their teachers and classmates questions about course material. Teachers can also provide resources online for students to review at their own

pace. Google Drive is used for the creation and distribution of assignments, while Google Docs, Sheets, and Slides are used for writing, Gmail is used for communication, and Google Calendar is used for scheduling, all within the same platform: Google Classroom.

More and more students, either because of physical limitations or personal preferences, are turning to online distance education to fulfil their educational needs. They include those who live too far away from a university to commute, people who work full-time and can only study at or after work, people who have other commitments during the day, and people who simply prefer independent study. Online courses are only accessible to students who have access to a computer, the Internet, and the drive to succeed in a non-traditional learning environment. The convenience of taking a course from anywhere in the world at any time makes online education a great alternative to traditional classroom settings.

The flexibility of online courses allows students to study whenever it is most practical for them. Many modern students are attracted to online courses because they may be accessed at any time, day or night, from any computer with Internet connectivity. Online education describes courses taken entirely online. Distance learning, however, encompasses all non-classroom-based learning that takes place over a physical distance, not just online learning. Changes in how we instruct and are instructed are being sparked by the rise of online learning. The traditional model of teaching, in which professors lecture to an audience of mostly silent students, is giving way to one in which students and teachers work together to design and implement lessons. Rather from being the "sage on the stage," instructors are increasingly taking on the role of "guide by the side."

CONSTRUCTIONS AND COLLABORATION

According to this point of view, people consciously build up their knowledge through experience with the world around them. Using this approach, students are actively involved in the "co-creation" of their educational experience. Students are encouraged to take an active role in their own education rather than only receiving material to memorise for tests. Rather than merely publishing and analysing the material you think your students need to know, a good educator focuses on the experiences that will generate the most learning from the student's perspective. Each individual in a class has the potential to, and indeed should, play the role of both instructor and student.

The teacher is no longer just a source of information, but also a mentor and an example to follow. By moderating discussions and activities in a way that guides students collectively towards the class's wider learning objectives, you engage students in ways that address their particular learning requirements. Many language classrooms around the world may look and feel very different to today's teachers than they did when we were in school. In teacher education seminars and other forms of professional development, the teacher might have heard the terms "21st-century skills" and "new literacies" discussed. In order to be productive members of the globalised society of the future, many of us have concluded that today's students need to acquire new skill sets. However, for many pressed-for-time educators, these cutting-edge competencies and ideas may be opaque or difficult to implement in the classroom. The digital tools will be used to analyse some of the most significant shifts in 21st century education, and the implications of these shifts for the global dissemination of the English language will be discussed.

These are now considered fundamental for students in the 21st century, and their introduction has influenced educational systems all around the world. Simply put, 21st century skills are the set of abilities that individual needs to thrive in a world that is increasingly interconnected, digitally advanced, collaborative, creative, resource-hungry, and open to new ways of doing things and ways of thinking. The prominence and significance of English have skyrocketed over the past several decades as a result of its emergence as a global language. It may be impossible to achieve the necessary English language learning objectives in the current global setting if language teachers stick to teaching the way they always have. Learners were not provided with opportunities for creativity and constructiveness in the past to hone these four language abilities. (LSRW). Technology constantly develops to meet the shifting demands of the time.

The 21st century we find ourselves in is a period of rapid technological development. Therefore, the most recent trend in English instruction is the employment of contemporary technical instruments, as their availability has had a substantial effect on the teaching of English.

Conclusion

Many areas of the language classroom have benefited from technology developments. In order to maximise its potential as a pedagogical resource, English language instructors should wholeheartedly embrace technological progress. This new approach to education has been universally lauded and enthusiastically adopted by educators, students, and parents. Students' passion and motivation have increased since switching to this method. The emphasis in classrooms is now on the learner, rather than the teacher.

One of the ultimate goals of employing cutting-edge technology in the classroom is to encourage students to actively engage in the process of learning English in order to develop useful, real-world proficiency. In today's tech-enabled, collaborative classrooms, students are not only allowed, but actively encouraged, to share ideas and information with one another. The future of English language education is bright, and it is clear that multimedia will play a crucial role in today's student-focused, cutting-edge classrooms. As a result, a thorough evaluation of English language abilities to boost general communication competency would promote the quality of instruction and the application of students to modern educational foundations. Current methods of teaching and learning are opaque, incomprehensible, and unintelligible unless they are digitised.

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